

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE VALUE APPROACH IN THE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

J.K.Fozilov

Researcher (DSc) of the Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan
named after T.N.Qori Niyoz

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***Abstract.** One of the main features in the process of studying in upper classes of general secondary education is the rapid formation of the student's personality. Consistency and continuity in the approach to values will expand their achievements and influence. This leads to look at the events at the level of value and depreciation. In this approach, the importance of value emerges. A value-based approach to teaching students in general secondary education institutions is also one of the main principles. This article served to illuminate the mechanisms of using value approaches in forming the spirituality and objective worldview of students of general secondary schools.*

***Keywords:** values, philosophy of values, axiology, axiological approach, students, secondary schools, education system, principle of continuity, value approach, objective worldview, development of student's objective worldview.*

The whole life of a person consists of the process of improving personal values, perfecting one's value, striving to understand the value of others, society, time and the changes taking place in it. In order to realize the value of one's own personality and others, the spiritual image and world formed during the maturation of a person should serve goodness, have high social qualities, and he should be educated to the extent that he understands the essence and purpose of life. In this sense, Socrates' "know thyself!" - slogan is very important.

The value of a person is manifested in the dialectical relationship with the time he lives in, the processes in it, social and historical conditions. The demands of the environment and time shape and refine the value of the individual, and he himself moves towards a deeper understanding of how his value is related to his personal requirements, needs and goals. Values allow young people to have a deeper understanding of the meaning of life, to use the rules of society correctly, to adapt their behavior to the requirements of these moral criteria [3].

In the current period, it is extremely urgent to convey to students and pupils the essence of the processes of appreciation and depreciation, to achieve a correct explanation of the importance of the values declared by independence.

It is extremely important to teach the basics of modern axiology, that is, value science, which is a set of knowledge about the sense of value and appreciation, the category of values, their essence, content, and forms of manifestation, in the education and formation of young people, especially students and pupils, as representatives of a spiritually mature generation. For this reason, one of the main criteria of educational effectiveness is the use of knowledge fields that summarize the achievements of the entire humanity in terms of values.

The science of axiology, which is widespread in the West, is one of the scientific fields that is one of the theoretical bases for the practice of many principles of human values and rights in developed countries [2].

The axiological approach in the educational system has its own characteristics, and in this process, it requires taking into account the nature of the students' activities, thinking characteristics, needs and interests, development opportunities specific to their age. At the same time, in order to improve the process of education, acquiring knowledge, skills, qualifications, the breadth of worldview, the ability to get out of difficult situations in the educational environment, the acquisition of ideological-political, spiritual-ethical qualities, patriotism, awareness in moral actions, correctness, precision, Taking into account their abilities, temperament, and character traits in developing the qualities of intelligence, intelligence, and creativity, as well as strengthening their emotional and volitional stability, encouraging them to work together as a team, values create great opportunities in the pedagogical and psychological correct approach. However, at each age stage, there are opportunities for personal development, and it is necessary to take these opportunities into account when influencing them physically, mentally, and morally. After all, age and individual characteristics of personality development make special demands on education.

An individual approach to teaching students in general secondary educational institutions is also one of the main principles. One of the main features in the process of studying in upper classes of general secondary education is the rapid formation of the student's personality. In this period, it is important to prepare the student for social life, to acquire the necessary mental abilities for social maturity. In this period, even if the students' character develops a desire for maturity, internal contradictions also appear in this regard. Apathy and indifference also appear in some of the students. In such a situation, it is important to arouse interest in learning, self-awareness, and activeness in students. Although this process is very complicated, it is very important to develop the most important qualities: initiative, independence, ingenuity, perseverance, thirst for knowledge.

Psychologists such as B.G.Ananov, I.S.Kon, A.V.Petrovsky, M.G.Davletshin, E.G.Goziev also believe that with the strengthening of the conscious motivation of students to study in an educational institution, they gradually get used to new conditions. , think about starting to understand their rights and duties. Pupils' initial feeling of being under parental control, feeling free in a new environment, begins to affect their studies and behavior. However, his material and spiritual dependence on his parents and school causes a number of conflicts and contradictions. Gradually, these contradictions are eliminated, and as a result of having certain experience and knowledge bases, their beliefs are formed based on their views on social life, their attitude to values, and their understanding of their identity. They will acquire skills and competencies to manage their own behavior. An opportunity to put theoretical and practical knowledge into practice begins to arise. This depends on the student's ability to properly organize his educational activities, plan his free time appropriately, work on books, etc. If this activity is carried out consistently at all stages of education, the student will get deep and solid knowledge, and will also ensure that he matures as a real citizen of the society and a mature specialist [1].

Cooperation between the teacher and students is one of the important factors in achieving educational efficiency. After all, this cooperation is an important means of mastering the educational material. Some psychologists, for example, the group of V.Ya.Lyudis, in expressing

the role of teacher-student cooperation in the formation of new mental qualities, define that the formation of educational activity is not the basis of learning the basics of science, but the process of acquiring socio-cultural values of a person. But when summing up the opinion of all scientists, the method of cooperative activity means the system of joint actions of the teacher and the student. This begins with the teacher's management of the student, the student's activity increases and becomes a practical and mental activity controlled by them, and the relationship between the teacher and the student becomes cooperative.

Along with psychological-pedagogical peculiarities, the educational-pedagogical process also has its own characteristics, in which, along with the formation of students' knowledge and skills, it educates a mentally and physically mature, socially active person who expresses spiritual and moral qualities. The basis of the pedagogical process is the spiritual and moral education of decency, goodness, honesty, trust, and respect. Pedagogical process in general secondary educational institutions is multifaceted and requires attention to increase the effectiveness of preparation for successful implementation of mutual educational organization. In general, one of the important features of the pedagogical process is the knowledge, skills and abilities, theoretical knowledge and concepts acquired by the students, the system of rules is the basis of the activity of the educational process. In this regard, having knowledge, qualifications and skills within the scope of school subjects; to have broad psychological-pedagogical knowledge, ability; pedagogical thinking and pedagogical etiquette, pedagogical technique; having ideological belief, moral image, spiritual elevation, internal culture, organization, patience, perseverance, pedagogical ability; It is one of the main features of the composition of qualities such as demandingness and strict discipline.

In the educational process, attitudes such as lack of self-control, rudeness, arrogance, undermining their value among peers or the group, lying, mistrust, inattention, indifference, irresponsibility have a negative effect on the teacher-student relationship in the formation of an objective worldview of the student's personality. During the school period, students differ from each other in terms of material, spiritual and family conditions. This, in turn, requires an individual approach in choosing or implementing means of influence on them. It is impossible to define the sphere of influence in education and upbringing in the same way for everyone in order not to create psychological conflicts with the student.

In the organization of the educational process, not in the way of forcing students, but taking into account the individual characteristics of each student, a creative approach to work, organization of socio-political, educational work in accordance with the purpose, being an example for them in every work, understanding the demands and needs, strict internal discipline of the school it is important to observe, fully acquire theoretical knowledge in class, take care when needed, learn experience and traditions, values and implement them creatively. First of all, in bringing out the intellectual potential of students, it is necessary to educate the attitude towards the formation of an objective worldview with the knowledge within the educational subjects. Demanding in education should be carried out in accordance with pedagogical ethics, taking into account the level of students. This, in turn, largely depends on the pedagogical and psychological principles of teaching and the pedagogical skills of teachers. It is the effectiveness of this process that changes the student's attitude to education. So, in order to achieve efficiency in mastering subjects and acquiring knowledge in the process of education, students should:

- taking into account their extremely impressionable nature, lack of willpower, lack of self-control, and in some cases their arrogance, increasing their demands without knocking their personal dignity to the ground;

- taking into account the background of the students and the fact that they grew up in different conditions, it is appropriate to choose the methods and tools that affect them and to have an individual approach.

Taking into account that the above requirements are organized on the basis of a valuable approach to the formation of an objective worldview of students, together with the acquisition of knowledge in this regard, high collective education, at the same time, the study of the psyche of each student, helps to determine their capabilities, as well as the psyche, mind, activity of each student learning, helps to organize it correctly and, most importantly, has a developmental function, teaches each student to analyze the mind, environment, interaction with others, and finally forms and improves the student's mastery, valuable attitude. As students acquire knowledge, skills and abilities both in class and in practical training, in the process of educational work, as well as in extracurricular activities, it is necessary to take into account the above-mentioned psychological characteristics.

In general, in the process of studying the analysis of pedagogical and psychological literature within the subject, firstly, students are armed with knowledge on the choice and orientation of future professions, secondly, they are introduced to the components of their consciousness and activity related to the psyche of the student's personality, and thirdly, students are introduced to the variability of human psychology, helps to determine its laws and mechanisms. Because the changes that occur in the personality of the student during adolescence are directly focused on the formation of an objective worldview based on the axiological approach, and they are directed to know the laws of preparing them both mentally and physically for educational activities in the educational process. This requires taking into account the following:

- impact on the personality of each student in the educational process;
- taking into account the state of student activity in the educational environment;
- to determine the pedagogical and psychological laws of forming and developing an objective worldview of students based on the axiological approach;
- to explain to the students the essence of the existing value relationship in the objective world;
- preparation of psychological-pedagogical descriptions of students, etc.

In order to carry out such tasks, firstly, it is necessary for students to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities, and secondly, psychological preparation for the development of intellectual potential as a result of theoretical and practical training. Psychological preparation is characterized by the organization of the educational process aimed at forming the psychological and pedagogical qualities of students.

Psychological qualities prepare students for the military process from a spiritual and spiritual point of view, guide them to conscious activity. Because the student emerges with the improvement of mental processes and quality changes of the individual.

Determining the causes of behavior in the educational process, the essence of the spiritual and cultural event, events that happened in the student community, their achievements and shortcomings; arranging psychological counseling for students in determining their future plans; It is important to determine the sphere of influence by helping them to show mutual discipline,

sense of responsibility, ingenuity, responsiveness, stability in class, extracurricular and extracurricular activities. Because in the current period, the activity of providing knowledge to students has changed radically, and the formation of an axiological approach to their occupation in the future is of great importance in the process of knowing in education. It is directly related to the development of students' objective worldview in the educational process

and without acquiring other knowledge, it is impossible to educate students' spirituality. In this regard, the inclusion of values in the content of education will form and develop feelings of honesty, tolerance, respect, hatred against violence, intolerance to negative behavior, striving to increase the power of one's country, state, and trust. Through values, psychological preparation is carried out in a unique way when students understand the objective concepts of the surrounding peers, adult community, school environment and society in the educational process.

Consistency and continuity in the approach to values will expand their achievements and influence. This leads to look at the events at the level of value and depreciation. In this approach, the importance of value emerges. In this regard, as the philosopher and scientist K.Nazarov noted, a comprehensive approach is also important in the axiological approach: "The impact of events in the universe on the life of our planet, the processes taking place on earth on people's lives and lifestyles, the need to save humanity as a result of ecological destruction and the danger of war, the human race and the most living things. it is better to rely on an axiological approach to properly understand their value as valuable possessions".

The problems that have arisen in the course of the current globalization require an assessment based on an axiological approach to social events and phenomena. In this regard, it is necessary to pay attention to the value of ancestors, their social importance for humanity, their distinction in terms of value, and their uniqueness. In studying the basics of science, attention is paid to the significance of the main achievements of each period, the development of society, the development of culture, and spiritual heritage. That's why in military education, the values of wars, military service should not be used to harm human life, but to serve to prevent ecological destruction, weapons of mass destruction.

In short, the axiological approach in forming an objective worldview of students has its own characteristics, it is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities, the breadth of the worldview, the ability to get out of difficult situations, the acquisition of ideological-political, spiritual-moral qualities, awareness, correctness, accuracy, The axiological (value) approach creates great opportunities in pedagogical-psychological training, such as ingenuity, thoughtfulness, creative qualities in the acquisition of knowledge, taking into account the characteristic features, emotional-will stability, learning to act together. Among these opportunities, systematization of the values used in education to understand the concepts of tolerance, honesty, patriotism, friendship, responsibility, faith, respect, relying on certain criteria in this regard, requires studying each academic subject itself as a value.

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